

MOLECULAR DETECTION OF *SALMONELLA* SPP ISOLATED FROM DIARRHOEIC HUMAN, SHEEP AND GOATS IN BAGHDAD GOVERNORATE BY MULTIPLEX PCR

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Abstract

The current study examined the frequency of the 4 virulence genes from *salmonella* spp. isolated from diarrhoeic people and animals (sheep and goats) in the Baghdad governorate between October 2021 and February 2022. A total of 300 fecal samples were obtained from 100 diarrheal people, 100 sheep, and 100 goats. All faecal samples were pre-enriched in Tetrathionate broth and Rappaport Vassiliadis R10 broth before being tested for the presence of *salmonella* spp. After being sub cultured on SS and XLD agar, the broth culture was incubated at 37 °C for 24 to 48 hours. Standard biochemical assays and the Vitek GN test were used to identify the isolates, and multiplex PCR was used to identify the virulence genes of *salmonella* spp. Primers were employed in the current work to amplify the (*invA*, *fliC*, *fljB*, and *rfbJ*) genes, which were chosen from four distinct genes. The findings indicated that the prevalence of *Salmonella* spp. was (78) isolates representing (26%) in all the samples, with sheep feces having the highest prevalence rate of 11%, followed by human feces (10%) and goat feces (5%)., 33 isolates belonged to *serovar Typhimurium*, 9 isolates belonged to *serovar Typhi*, 23 isolates belonged to *serovar Enteritidis*, and 13 isolates belonged to *serovar arizonae*. *Salmonella Typhi* were identified by the presence of the specific amplified products to (*fliC* and *invA*) genes while *S. enteritidis* were identified by the presence of *invA* genes only while *Salmonella. arizonae* were identified by the presence of (*invA*, *fljB*, and *rfbJ*) genes. all isolates of *Salmonella* were positive for the *invA* gene amplified

Key Word: multiplex PCR, virulence genes, *salmonella* spp.

Introduction

Salmonella is one of the most common and economically important zoonotic pathogens (Hawwas *et al.*, 2022) that pose health risks for people and animals (Balasubramanian *et al.*, 2019) , gastrointestinal tracts of Warm-blooded animals are home to *Salmonella* spp. *Salmonellosis*, often known as food poisoning, is a condition that affects people and is mostly characterized by moderate diarrhea (Hennekinne *et al.*, 2015) Depending on the severity of the illness and the immunological health of the affected person, *salmonellosis* may be lethal (W H O, 2018). Generally, *Salmonella* infection in humans ranges from a self-limiting condition to a life-threatening and may causes death in children, old people, and immunodeficient persons (Abuaita *et al.*, 2021) In addition to the commonly known food-borne infection route, humans can become infected through interactions with live infected animals and environments that contaminated with animal fecal matter, followed by the subsequent accidental ingestion of the bacteria (Cummings *et al.*, 2012). Moreover, gastrointestinal tracts of animal that associated with this pathogen may contaminate the

carcass and easily be transferred to the flesh, organ surfaces, fleece, and skin during meat processing. Additionally, this may occur indirectly through contamination of human hands by intestinal content or by fecal matter of animals slaughterhouse (Thomas *et al.* 2020). *Salmonella* cause significant economic loss both directly and indirectly, directly via mortality and poor growth following clinical sickness, and indirectly, through animal carriage that results in human instances of economic losses result from chronic illness, poor development performance, and other expenditures such as treatment, diagnostics, labor, veterinary intervention, as well as mortality. These other costs are in addition to labor costs (Bazeley, 2003). *Salmonella* pathogenesis depends on a large number of virulence genes, many of which are found on the chromosome, plasmids, integrated bacteriophage DNA, *Salmonella* pathogenicity islands (SPIs), and *Salmonella* genomic islands (SGIs) of the genome (Card *et al.*, 2016). the *invA* gene, which is responsible for *Salmonella's* invasion of host epithelial cells and is used as a specific marker for the rapid detection of *Salmonella* (Eng *et al.*, 2105), and the enterotoxin production *stn* gene that is involved in the complex mechanism of diarrhea due to *Salmonella* infection (Sabry *et al.*, 2020). These genes can be used to identify *Salmonella* in samples of the natural environment, food, and feces, Virulence chromosomal genes like as *invA*, *invE*, *himA*, and *phoP* are the targets for species-specific PCR amplification. (Jamshidi *et al.* 2009) the invasion A (*invA*) is one of the most researched virulence factors that is employed as a biomarker for the identification of *Salmonella* spp (El-Sebay *et al.*, 2017). Numerous investigations have shown the identification of *Salmonella* spp specially *S. Typhi* possible by using PCR targeted for the (*fliC* gene, *ViaB*, *rfbE*, and *rfbS*) genes (Hashimoto *et al.*, 1995). These results, however, demonstrated that multiplex PCR employing a number of targeted genes was required for the precise identification of *S. Typhi* and that each primer pair was not unique to *S. Typhi* This study aims to knowing the occurrence and the virulence of *Salmonella* serovars in sheep and goats in Baghdad / Iraq associated risks of the person in the study area

Materials and methods :

Isolation and Identification

Sample collection

300 fecal samples altogether Between October 2020 and February 2021, were collected from 100 sheep, 100 goats, and 100 humans who had mucoid or bloody diarrhea in various regions of the Baghdad Governorate. To expeditiously cultivate fecal samples for bacteriological analysis, they were brought to the lab in a cold chamber container. One gram of each fecal sample (from a human, sheep, or goat) was diluted in 3 mL of sterile saline. As discussed by Quinn *et al.*, (2002), samples were grown and identified. a loopful of the diluted specimens was inoculated into Tetrathionate broth (TTB) containing 2% iodine-iodide solution for 24 hours at 37 C in order to isolate *Salmonella* bacteria (United States Pharmacopoeia 2005 and American Public Health Association 1998)) Then, 0.1 ml of TTB culture was selectively enriched in 10 ml of Rappaport Vassiliadis R10 broth (Difco) It was incubated in F broth for 24 hours, with an additional night of incubation at 37 °C. aloopful was then streaked out onto MacConkey's agar, xylose lysine deoxycholate, and *Salmonella-Shigella* agar medium and incubated for 18 to 24 hours at 37 °C.

colonies exhibiting morphological traits that are typical of *Salmonella* species, Red colonies growing on XLD agar with or without black centers were selected, purified, according to Collee *et al.*, (1996). suspected colonies were examined biochemically by applying the Gram stain, oxidase and catalase activities, triple sugar iron slants (TSI), and lysine agar plates, all isolates were tested to distinguish them at the species level. The isolates were subsequently studied Following enrichment, the samples underwent multiplex PCR analysis and DNA extraction using the boiling procedure (Lee *et al.*, 2009).

Extraction DNA of isolated *Salmonella*:

Salmonella typhimurium, *Salmonella typhi*, *Salmonella enteritidis*, and *Salmonella enterica serovar S.arizonae* colonies were among the three to five colonies that were selected from each plate and sub-cultured onto Muller-Hinton agar plates. The DNA from each isolate was then extracted using the Genomic DNA Purification (G_spin dna extraction kit, intron biotechnology). was carried out in line with the manufacturer's instructions. after measuring the DNA with the NanoDrop 1000 Spectrophotometer, Kit (Fisher Scientific, Pittsburgh, PA) Depending on the DNA marker (1000 bp DNA ladde), the amplified DNA products from *Salmonella* spp. were examined using electrophoresis on 1% agarose gel stained with ethidium bromide and seen by UV light. the following To establish the isolates' identities, the amplified DNA products were submitted to species-specific MPCR analysis.

Multiplex PCR

Four sets of primer virulence gene pairs were employed for the multiplex PCR. The order of primers utilized in this research is displayed in (Table1) *Salmonella typhimurium*, *Salmonella typhi*, *Salmonella enteritidis*, and *Salmonella enterica serovar S.arizonae* species confirmation by analysis of the amplified DNA from all isolates was done as a control for DNA extraction (*invA*, *fliC*, *fliB*, *rflB* gene) The multiplex PCR protocol created by Latha *et al.*(2014) served as the foundation for the primers and the screening technique employed for the samples. These genes were amplified many times using PCR in a process that used a (5ul Taq PCR PreMix G_SPIN kit, 10 picomols/ul of forward primer, and 10 picomols/ul of reverse primer (1ul) Reverse primer for every primer, 1.5 of DNA, and 16.5 of distiller water performed in a multi-master mix with a final volume of 25 ul (Tabl 2)

gene	Prime length (bp r		Sequence	Tm (°C)	GC (%)	Product size
<i>fliC</i>	24	Forward	5'- CCCCCTTGACCATTCTACCGATA -3	70	73.54	183 Lim <i>et al.</i> (2003)
	24	Reverse	5'- CCGTATAGGACATTGTCAACGTCG -3	72	73.88	
<i>invA</i>	26	Forward	5'- AACGGGCTTGCACCGCTATTAAAGTG3'- '3	78	76.04	284 bp Zahraei <i>et al.</i>

	22	Reverse	5'- CCAAGGAAACTGCCACGCTACT -'3	68	73.18	(2007)
<i>fljB</i>	24	Forward	5'- CCAATGTCTTCGGCATGGTAAGCA - '3	72	73.88	526 bp Lim <i>et al.</i> (2003)
	24	Reverse	5'- GGCTTCAGCAATGATAGCTGCCAT -'3	72	73.88	
<i>rfbJ</i>	24	Forward	5'-- CATAGTTCAACCTTGACCACGACC - '3	72	73.88	663 bp Lim <i>et al.</i> (2003)
	24	Reverse	5'- ACGAATGGTTATTTTCGGCCTTCGG '3	72	73.88	

Table 1 The specific primer of genes used in this study

Component	25 µL (Final volume)
Taq PCR PreMix	5µl
Forward primer	10 picomols/µl (1 µl)
Reverse primer	10 picomols/µl (1 µl)
DNA	1.5µl
Distill water	16.5 µl

Table (2): Reaction components of PCR.

Polymerase chain reaction of targeted virulence genes

After conducting numerous experiments to determine the best conditions for initial denaturation and annealing, the temperature was changed using gradient PCR for all samples to determine the best conditions, and the concentration of the DNA template was changed from 1.5-2 l to take into account these two important factors in primer annealing with complement. *Salmonella* species' virulence genes were quickly and precisely detected under the following cycle conditions: 5 minutes of beginning incubation at 94 C then 45 rounds of denaturation at 94 C for 35 cycles elongation at 72 °C for 45 sec, annealing at 62 °C for 1 min, and then 10 min of final extension in one cycle at 72 °C. amplification Responses were carried out in a master-gradient thermocycler (Eppendorf). *Salmonella* spp. amplified DNA products were examined, sorted, and visualized using 1.5% agarose gel electrophoresis and ultraviolet illumination (302 nm) following red staining at 5 volts per cm². 1:30 hours in 1x TBE buffer, depending on the DNA marker (1000 bp DNA ladder)(table 3).

No.	Phase	Tm (°C)	Time	No. of cycle
1-	Initial Denaturation	94°C	5 min.	1 cycle
2-	Denaturation -2	94°C	45sec	35 cycle
3-	Annealing	62°C	1min	
4-	Extension-1	72°C	45 sec	
5-	Extension -2	72°C	10 min.	1 cycle

Table (3) The optimum condition of detection (*invA*, *fliC*, *fljB*, *rfbJ* gene)

Results & Discussion :

Identification of *Salmonella* spp (Phenotypic and Biochemical Test) :-

The presumptive salmonella colony from selective media in (45) isolates that grew on XLD agar plates had red colonies with black centers, figure (1 A) , while Colony morphology of 33 isolates of salmonella were colonies appear as yellow pigmented with black centers figure (1 B). Growth is visible on the plating media within 24 to 48 hours of incubation, salmonella colonies round, convex, and Gram negative, rods or coccobacilli

B

A

figure (1 A and figure (1 B) Growth of *Salmonella* spp on selective XLD agar plates

Percentage of Isolation of *Salmonella* spp

Salmonella organisms were found in the collected fecal samples from diarrheal humans and animals (sheep and goats) according to the results of bacteriological. The outcomes of the bacterial isolation revealed that While 222 samples from diverse urban and rural farm animals in different areas of the Baghdad Governorate yielded .examination negative findings for bacterial culture (78) bacterial isolates from three hundred diarrheic fecal samples were identified as salmonella and represent(26%.) as showing in (table 4) among the three hundred diarrheic fecal samples, 33 (11%) were found to be *Salmonella typhimurium* , and 23 (7%) were found to be *Salmonella enteritidis* , 13 (4.3%) isolates belonged to serovar *Salmonella arizonae*, and 9 (3%) isolates belonged to serovar *Salmonella Typhi* ,The distribution of the identified *Salmonella* serotypes in human samples in relation to their history of contact with animals

The prevalence of *Salmonella* spp. in different hosts was determined and it was found that the highest prevalence was in sheep 33(11%) (10 isolates were found to be *Salmonella typhimurium* and *Salmonella Enteritidis* , 13 isolates were found to be *Salmonella arizonae* , followed by human 30(10%) (15 isolates found to be *typhimurium* , 9 isolates diagnosed as *Typhi* , 6 culterd as *Enteritidis* , while goats 15(5%) (8 and 7 isolates recavoerd as *typhimurium* and *Enteritidis* respectively (table 4)

Type	number of isolate	percentage	Host		
			Sheep	Human	Goat
<i>S typhimurium</i>	(300)33	11%	10	15	8
<i>S enteritidis</i>	(300) 23	7%	10	6	7
<i>S arizonae</i>	(300)13	4.3%	13		
<i>S Typhi</i>	(300) 9	3%		9	
Total	78		33(11%)	30(10%)	15(5%)

Table(4) percentage and Distrbuiation of *Salomnela* isolates in different host in Baghdad governorate

Virulence determinants in *Salmonella* serotypes from sheep, goats, and humans

A total of 300 samples of diarrheal fecal samples from human and animals (sheep and goats) with fever, mucoid, or bloody diarrhea were brought to the lab from various locations throughout the Baghdad Governorate. Pathogens were then identified and evaluated using multiplex-PCR assays, multiplex-enrichment culture, and electrophoresis. *Salmonella typhimurium*, *Salmonella enteritidis*, *Salmonella arizonae*, and *Salmonella Typhi* were identified by looking at the target specific fragment of the virulence gene that is used to identify *Salmonella* genus or serovars isolates. these genes are(*invA*, *fliC*, *fljB*, and *rfbJ*) and their band sizes are (283 bp, 183 bp, 526 bp, and (Figure 2, 3,4)

As a result, all 78 *Salmonella* isolates, comprising 33 *S. typhimurium*, 23 *S. enteritidis*, 13 *Salmonella arizonae*, and 9 *Salmonella Typhi*, isolated from host fecal samples (human, sheep, and goat), revealed presence of *invA* genes in ratio (100%) only the isolate of the serovar *S. Typhimurium* from sheep, goats, and humans showed that all of the virulence genes (*invA*, *fliC*, *fljB*, and *rfbJ*) were present in ratio 33 (100%) In contrast, *Salmonella.arizonae* isolates from sheep exhibit the presence of all virulence genes except *fliC* genes, while *S Typhi* isolates from humans exhibit (*invA*, *fliC*,) in ratio 9(100%). all 23 isolates of serovar *S. Enteritidis* were found in diarrheic stool samples from both humans and animals exhibited presence of *invA* genes only Tables (5) Figures 2, 3, and 4 show specific outcomes of the MPCR detection of the four virulence genes in the four *salmonella* isolates collected from human and animals fecal.

Species	No	No. of <i>salmonella</i> isolates positive for virulence genes (%)			
		<i>invA</i>	<i>fliC</i>	<i>fljB</i>	<i>rfbJ</i>
<i>S typhimurium</i>	33	33 (100%)	33(100%)	33(100%)	33(100%)
<i>S enteritidis</i>	23	23 (100%)	0	0	0
<i>S arizonae</i>	13	13(100%)	0	13(100%)	13(100%)
<i>S Typhi</i>	9	9(100%)	9 (100%)	0	0
<i>total</i>	78				

Table(5) Occurrence of virulence genes detected in *salmonella* isolates from host faecal sample

Figure (2) Multiplex PCR product of (human isolates) the band size (283 bp 183 bp, 526 bp, and 663 lane 1-15 represent of *Salmonella enterica subsp. enterica serovar Typhimurium*) diagnosed by specific genes (*invA, fliC, fljB, rfbJ*), lane 16-24 represent of (*Salmonella enterica subsp. enterica serovar Typhi*) diagnosed by presence of (*invA, fliC*) gene band size (283 bp 183 bp) respectively , lane 25-30 represent (*Salmonella enterica subsp. enterica serovar Enteritidis*) diagnosed by presence of (*invA,*) gene only in band size(283 bp) The product was electrophoresis on 1.5% agarose at 5 volt/cm². 1x TBE buffer for 1:30 hours. M: DNA ladder

(100-2000 bp)

Figure (3) Multiplex PCR product of (sheep isolates) the band size (283 bp 183 bp, 526 bp, and 663) lane **1-10** represent of (*Salmonella enterica subsp. enterica serovar Typhimurium*) diagnosed by specific genes (*invA*, *fliC*, *fljB*, *rfbJ*), lane **11-20** represent of (*Salmonella enterica subsp. enterica serovar Enteritidis*) diagnosed by presence of (*invA*), gene only in band size band size (283 bp), lane **21-33** represent (*Salmonella enterica subsp. enterica serovar arizonae*) diagnosed by presence of (*invA*, *fljB*, *rfbJ*) genes in band size (283 bp 526 bp, and 663) respectively, The product was electrophoresis on 1.5% agarose at 5 volt/cm². 1x TBE buffer for 1:30 hours. M: DNA ladder (100-2000 bp).

Figure (4) Multiplex PCR product of (goat isolates) the band size (283 bp 183 bp, 526 bp, and 663) lane **1-8** represent of (*Salmonella enterica subsp. enterica serovar Typhimurium*) diagnosed by specific genes (*invA*, *fliC*, *fljB*, *rfbJ*), lane **9-15** represent of (*Salmonella enterica subsp. enterica serovar Enteritidis*) diagnosed by presence of (*invA*), gene only in band size band size (283 bp), , The product was electrophoresis on 1.5% agarose at 5 volt/cm². 1x TBE buffer for 1:30 hours. M: DNA ladder (100-2000).

DISCUSSION

All *salmonella* isolates from different hosts in this study were associated with different types of diarrhea (mild, moderate, and severe), but their severity and type of diarrhea differed from mucoid and/or bloody diarrhea. This difference in severity and type of diarrhea could be attributed to the fact that these types of *salmonella* possessed virulence genes that were in charge of producing toxins, such as (*invA*, *fliC*) genes that are linked to invasiveness and adherence as discussed by (Paul *et al.*, 2021) who concluded that In the case of *salmonellosis* fever, anorexia, dehydration, and mucus in diarrheic feces were the most prevalent clinical signs, and diarrhea may be caused by a primary or secondary immune deficit represented by a stressful circumstance, such heat stress, which renders immune systems unable to prevent the development of clinical illness.

In the current study most of *salmonella* colonies isolates (45) isolates that grew on XLD agar plates had red colonies with black centers because non-lactose fermenters and appear as pink with black center as well as (33) isolates were colonies yellow pigmented and some with black centers figure (1 A) and figure (1 B) because they are both presumptive. The final confirmation was based on molecular PCR methods and the positive amplification of the genus specific biomarker, the (*invA*, *fliC*, *fljB*, *rfbJ*) genes several studies have reported that *salmonella* spp specially *S. enterica* serovar *Typhimurium* and other *S. enterica* serovars grow as yellow colonies on XLD agar (Hurley *et al*, 2018) this could attributed to the fact that these isolates may be horizontally inherited the lactose fermentation gene from *E. coli* (Leonard *et al*, 2015)

According to recent investigations, there were (78) isolates of *Salmonella* spp. in ratio (26%), in all samples. Goat feces produced the fewest isolates (5%), 33 of which belonged to serovar *Typhimurium*, 9 of which belonged to serovar *Typhi*, 23 of which belonged to serovar *Enteritidis*, and 13 of which belonged to serovar *arizonae*. isolated from livestock our study contributed with (AL-Darraji, and yousif, 2012) who showed that goat had low isolation rate compared with other enterobacteriacee sheep feces had the highest prevalence rate of 11%, followed by human feces (10%).this agreement with (Hawwas *et al.*, 2022) who concluded that the occurrence of *Salmonella* in sheep feces was higher than that in goat feces and human stool.

In the present study four different species were confirmed which constituted about this result similar to many researcher (Abouzeed, 1998). who recorded different species (*S.typhimurium*, 8; *S.agona*, 2; *S.infantis*, 1) and a study of other workers (Yousif, 2013) who isolated *Salmonella anatum* *S.newport*, *S.enteritidis* and *S.ohio*

There are a number of factors, including farm management and biosecurity procedures, that can account for the variations in *Salmonella* spp prevalence geographical position, environmental factors, and herd number (Cho and Yoon, 2014) It has a high incidence of virulent *Salmonella* spp. and is located in an urban region where livestock mostly consumes preserved foods that may include trace amounts of chemicals and amino acids as opposed to while livestock in rural areas that graze on natural grass. It would account for the increased frequency of pathogenic *Salmonella* spp. as mentioned by. (Mthembu *et al* 2019.) also may be contributed to the fact that the food animals are a potential source of virulent *Salmonella* spp., exposing humans to zoonotic infections through potential exposure route via food or direct exposure. Similar findings have been reported

by **Adesiyun et al., (2001)**. The total incidence of *Salmonella* was low in goats (5%) isolated from diarrheic fecal samples, which may be related to goat having good cellular immunity compared to sheep and other species. *Salmonella* isolates revealed that *S. enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* were the most prevalent serotypes, representing 11% and 7%, respectively, while *S arizonae* was 4.3%. and *S Typhi* was 3%. The predominance of *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* among diarrheic livestock, detected in the present study could be attributed to that *S. Enteritidis* and *S. Typhimurium* had wide host range and are considered non-host-adapted serovars and they are less likely to establish a “carrier state” in the recovered animal and this study is compatible with **(Hawwas et al., 2022)** who concluded that the most frequently identified serotypes were *S. Typhimurium* from sheep feces, and *S. enteritidis* from both goat and human stool, this study supported by **(El-Seedy et al., 2016)** also in agreement with **(AL-zubaidy Hanoun & Al Samrrae, 2019)** who concluded that high isolation rate of *Salmonella Typhimurium* in human and sheep

The prevalence of other *salmonella* pathotypes, such as *Salmonella enterica* serovar *Typhi*, which causes typhoid fever and causes infections in both humans and animals, is minimal. according to previous surveys done by **(Faik et al., 2014)**, the infection may be impacted by regional, managerial, seasonal, and diagnostic variables **(Langoni et al. 2004)**. for the purpose of detecting the four crucial *Salmonella* virulence genes *invA*, *fliC*, *fljB*, and *rfbJ*, a multiplex PCR test was created. (table 5) all 78 were submitted to multiplex PCR assays for the detection of particular virulence genes, and all *Salmonella* isolates exhibited the presence of *invA* genes in ratio (100%) indicating the possibility of employing these genes for *Salmonella* identification this computed with **(Chaudhary et al., 2015)** who conclude that the *invA* genes can be used as specific targets for detection of *Salmonella* as they are conserved among the *Salmonella*. They come to the conclusion that because *Salmonella invA* genes are conserved, they may be exploited as specific targets for detection of *Salmonella*. Also our study contributed with **(Jwad, 2019)** who concluded that (*Inv-A*, and *Fli-C*, genes are one of the important genes in molecular diagnosis for *S. typhimurium* virulence pathogenic genes

According to **Bacci et al. (2006)**, **Jamshidi et al. (2008)** and **Hawwas et al., (2022)** *Salmonella* isolates frequently have the *invA* (invasive) gene, which has sequences exclusive to this species. the single serovar *S. Typhimurium* isolate from humans, sheep, and goats demonstrated the presence of all the investigated virulence genes (*invA*, *fliC*, *fljB*, *rfbJ*.) Figure(5) in Table (2,3,4) The use of these virulence genes in our study demonstrated the significance of using these genes to identify and diagnose *salmonella* and to distinguish it from other *Salmonella* serovars using multiplex PCR. This is consistent with **Shanmugasundaram and Radhika , (2009)** conclusion that use of multiplex-PCR using *rfbJ*, *fliC*, and *fljB* proved to be capable of identifying of *S. Typhimurium* specifically and differentiating it from other *Salmonella*. We conclude the use of multiplex PCR amplification with four sets of primers in the current study, allowed for the sensitive and specific detection of *Salmonella* species. This finding confirms the capacity of these particular primer sets to identify the isolates as *Salmonella*. Additionally, the Multiplex PCR test employed in this study may identify many pathogens at the same time by amplifying multiple target genes in a single reaction, which can reduce labor costs and save time, according to **(Latha et al.,2017)** .

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